

On the Energy Needs of Artificial Intelligence

A. Chawla

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Abstract

In this note the author presents an argument limiting the potential of AI models. The position is that AI will never supersede man.

Consider a large language model, quantum or classical, on Earth which utilizes some energy budget x and produces an intelligence $f(x)$. Imagine a larger model which consumes all the energy generated by the Sun. Finally consider a very large model which consumes all the energy generated by all the stars in the observable universe. Beyond these there is as yet no known source of energy. Thus assuming the functional relation between energy consumption and intelligence of an LLM, it is apparent that the intelligence hits a ceiling after consuming all available energy sources. In contrast, via meditation, rishis and sages are known to enter states of infinite mass (cf. the Autobiography of a Yogi [2]), and transcend general relativistic limitations, and concomitantly access infinite energy¹. By contrast, their Earthly energy consumption is miniscule and therefore sustainable. QED.

Our position aligns with Prof. N. Chomsky's publicly expressed opinions (on the limitations of AI) as well in some ways.

References

- [1] Aman Chawla and Salvatore Domenic Morgera. Mechanism of universal quantum computation in the brain. *Journal of Applied Mathematics and Physics*, 12(2):468–474, 2024.
- [2] Paramhansa Yogananda. *Autobiography of a Yogi: The Original 1946 Edition plus Bonus Material*. Crystal Clarity Publishers, 2005.

¹The universal brain quantum computation model of [1] provides one feasible route for this access.